

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HERZALLA****FIRST NAME: MOHANNA****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word for MAC Version 16.73

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
2. Research (Turabian 2018, 19-22)
3. Guide Your Work (Turabian 2018, 32)
4. Drafting Your Paper (Turabian 2018, 75-83)
5. Revision and Editing (EUCLID 2021, 11-12)

ELEVATING YOUR WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Becoming an expert in an applied discipline is challenging without proper guidance, and writing is no exception. Sure, writing an e-mail or a review on that bad latte you had is straightforward, but what if you need to write something of greater significance, like an academic paper or scholarly journal? “A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” by Kate L. Turabian serves as a guide for navigating those more intimidating writing tasks. The manual discusses the best writing practices to follow so your writing is clear, consistent, and presented accordingly. It breaks down the writing process into smaller, more manageable components, from the early stages of research and drafting to revising and citation practices. In this response paper, I will summarize my biggest takeaways from both the manual and the “ACA-401 Coursepack” which will help elevate writers of all levels.

2) STYLE GUIDE

Style guides are essential in writing as they help provide consistency. In the “ACA-401 Coursepack,” a style guide is defined as “a means of documenting your approach as a

writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 41). A style guide generally provides standards on formatting, sentence structure, and grammar to help writers present their ideas more effectively.

Widely employed in academic writing, the Turabian style recommended by EUCLID is based on the Chicago Manual of Style. It offers recommendations for paper formatting, citation, and bibliography styles. The two citation formats used in Turabian are notes-bibliography and author-date. While the physical and social sciences utilize the author-date style, the arts, literature, and history use the notes-bibliography format.

The Chicago Manual of Style's notes-bibliography system is comparable to the notes-bibliography system employed by the Turabian style when it comes to citations. In this approach, the author acknowledges the information's source by including a footnote or endnote in the text that provides pertinent citation information.

3) RESEARCH

The first step of the writing process is research. “A Manual for Writers” defines research as “a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that the researcher and others want to solve. Research thus includes the steps involved in presenting or reporting it. To be a true researcher, as we are using the term, you must share your findings and conclusions with others” (Turabian 2018, 19). Simply put, research is gathering information to answer a question and share conclusions with others.

When conducting research in the past, my focus has always been on the data collected and the credibility of their sources. While that is significant, “A Manual for Writers” suggests that research is more about how you present your findings to readers, “Your success as a researcher thus depends not just on how well you gather and analyze data but also on how you report your reasoning so that your readers can test and judge it before making your claims part of their knowledge and understanding” (Turabian 2018, 20). The success of your research is dependent on how well you present your findings to others. It isn't enough to just gather many facts on a topic but to report it well enough, so readers accept your claims and supporting evidence as their own.

To achieve this, you must demonstrate why the question you are answering is worth being asked, “Experienced researchers, however, know that they must do more than convince us that their answer is sound. They must also show us why their question was worth asking, how its answer helps us understand some bigger issue in a new way” (Turabian 2018, 20). Your research should matter to you, but also to others. This is why it is so crucial to figure out the “So What?” aspect of your research. This can be especially challenging depending on the root of your chosen topic, but “A Manual for Writers” shares the formula “I am working on X because I want to find out Y so that I can help others understand Z” (Turabian 2018, 20). By using this formula, you ensure your research is considering others as it progresses.

4) **GUIDE YOUR WORK**

Assuming you have landed on a focused topic, the next step is to create a roadmap that will help guide your work. Simple outlines are sufficient, but researchers find storyboards to be best as they do not force you to be as specific (Turabian 2018, 23). A storyboard allows you to visually see and organize your project from beginning to end. To start a storyboard, begin with your question and hypothesis at the top of a page. From there, you will have a page for each of your claims or arguments and ideas for evidence needed to support them. The purpose of this is not to solidify your writing but to guide it, so placeholders and educated guesses are acceptable. The final step is to review all pages and make sense of the order, narrative, and significance of your writing. It is important to remember that the storyboard is just a tool to guide your research and can adapt as your thinking and writing develops.

5) **DRAFTING YOUR PAPER**

There is no single best way of drafting. Some writers prefer to write slowly and extensively plan out each paragraph while others choose to write quickly and revisit their draft at the end. You should follow whichever method best works for you.

Regardless of your writing style, everyone should practice effective writing habits to become more efficient. “A Manual for Writers” encourages two great writing habits which will help with efficiency. The first is using headlines and key terms to track your writing: “Use headings—ideally full sentences—to break your draft into manageable chunks and to show how your sections are related to one another. Even if papers in your field do not ordinarily use headings and subheadings, you can still use them as you draft and delete them later. You can also use lists of key terms to keep yourself on track” (Turabian 2018, 76). Incorporating headlines or key terms into your drafts helps keep your writing relevant and structured in a logical order. Furthermore, it breaks down a daunting writing task into small manageable components while keeping it whole.

The second great writing habit to develop is learning to work through procrastination or writer’s block: “If you can’t seem to get started on a first draft or if you struggle to draft more than a few words, you may have writer’s block (...) you may be stuck because you have no goals or have goals that are too high; you may feel so intimidated by the size of the task that you do not know where to begin; you may feel that you have to make every sentence or paragraph perfect before you move on to the next one; you may just allow yourself to be easily distracted” (Turabian 2018, 83). Writer’s block and procrastination hinder the writing process, and if it occurs for non-medical reasons like not knowing where to begin, there are several techniques you may use to combat it. For example, you may set realistic goals. Setting goals helps to work through procrastination and writer’s block by keeping the focus on one task at a time as opposed to the entire project. Another technique is to limit distractions in your environment, such as your phone, social media, noise, etc. Figure out what is the source of your procrastination and practice removing it to improve your efficiency as a writer.

6) REVISION AND EDITING

As a writer, your audience should find your work to be easily understandable and readable. The goal is to make your point clearly and concisely, but this can be challenging with grammatical, punctuation, and spelling errors. As mentioned in the course pack “ACA-401” by Euclid University, “Essays get dramatically improved upon careful editing. An essay is often recommended to be kept aside for a few days before editing. This practice gives you time to think further about your answer and arguments and return to your essay with a fresh perspective” (EUCLID 2021, 11). Like drafting, the revision process should not be rushed but instead done thoroughly to improve the overall quality of your writing.

Some great revision suggestions the course pack recommends include checking the overall structure of your essay so that it is in a logical order, checking transition signals that readers can easily follow between sentences and paragraphs, and ensuring each paragraph relates to the argument. Revising your work can make all the difference and the opportunity to evaluate your work and gain a new outlook should be embraced.

7) CONCLUSION

“A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations” by Kate L. Turabian proves to be an invaluable resource for those seeking guidance in the realm of academic writing. This manual offers a comprehensive guide that equips writers with the tools and techniques to confidently tackle complex writing tasks. It breaks down the writing process into manageable components, ensuring that writers of all levels can navigate the challenges of research, drafting, revising, and citation practices. Coupled with the insights from the “ACA-401 Coursepack”, this response paper highlights my main takeaways from the two resources which will help elevate writers of all levels.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, Fourth ed. 2021. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth ed., University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.